

SOCIO-ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION AND WATER POLLUTION: A CASE STUDY IN THE DISTRICT OF SÃO PEDRO-GARANHUNS/PE

 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.21111037

Maria do Carmo dos Santos Silva

Works in Basic Education as a teacher for the final years of elementary school; Specialist in Geography teaching from the State University of Pernambuco - UPE - 2017; Graduated with a full degree in Geography from the State University of Pernambuco - UPE - 2014; carminha.santos1421@gmail.com

Poliana dos Santos Silva

She works in Education as a teacher in Early Childhood Education II and the Initial Years of Elementary School in rural schools, having participated in the Escola da Terra program – NUPEFEC/Federal University of Pernambuco (2025–2026). She holds a Bachelor's degree in Pedagogy from the Federal University of Agreste de Pernambuco (2025) and a Bachelor's degree in Biological Sciences from the University of Northern Paraná (2020). She is a specialist in Biology Teaching (2022) and in Institutional and Clinical Psychopedagogy (2021), both from FAVENI. Currently, she is pursuing postgraduate studies in... Literacy and Reading. poliana.ssilva2ufape.edu.br

Ana Paula dos Santos Silva

She works in Basic Education as a teacher in Early Childhood Education II, holds a Bachelor's degree in Pedagogy from the Federal University of Agreste de Pernambuco (2025), a Bachelor's degree in Pedagogy from the Northern University of Paraná (2021), and a postgraduate degree in Clinical and Institutional Psychopedagogy from FAVENI (2023). paula.ssilva@ufape.edu.br

Maria Aparecida dos Santos Silva Souza

Bachelor's degree in Pedagogy from Uniasselvi - 2025: Postgraduate student in Clinical and Institutional Psychopedagogy (ongoing) dmariaaparecidadossantossilva@gmail.com

Roberto da Silva*Master's student in Science Teaching and Mathematics Education - UEPB; ORCID ID:**<https://orcid.org/0009-0009-7162-1684>; silva.roberto@aluno.uepb.edu.br***ABSTRACT**

This study analyzes the pollution of the Canhoto River and its environmental impacts in the São Pedro District, in Garanhuns in the state of Pernambuco, highlighting the need to strengthen environmental education and implement public policies focused on sustainability. Its general objective was to inform students and foster an understanding of the role of environmental education, from a theoretical and practical perspective, in the elective classes for the final years of elementary school at the EFITI José Ferreira Sobrinho Full-Time School. The methodology included literature review, theoretical and practical classes, direct observation, and activities related to the reuse of materials and care for the environment. The results demonstrate that the transdisciplinary approach broadens the understanding of the phenomenon by integrating social, economic, political, and cultural dimensions into environmental conservation, encouraging conscious and responsible attitudes among students. The practical classes were the most engaging, as they consolidated content, promoted playful learning, and fostered critical reflection and the internalization of sustainable values. Furthermore, the students came to recognize the importance of preserving local water resources. It is concluded that transdisciplinary environmental education contributes to reducing local pollution, strengthening an ecological culture, and encouraging practices contextualized to the school environment, providing support for pedagogical planning and the formulation of preventive and educational public policies for the community.

Keywords: Environment. Pollution. Lefty River.

INTRODUCTION

This article stems from an elective course offered in the second semester of 2023 to 6th and 7th grade students, entitled "Environmental Education in the District of São Pedro". The proposal is based on the importance of Environmental Education in the formation of critical, conscious individuals committed to sustainability. As a diversified part of the curriculum, the course allows students to choose topics of interest, expanding formative experiences and developing skills.

In this context, Environmental Education sought to promote awareness of environmental problems and encourage sustainable practices aimed at preserving natural resources. Among the main challenges are deforestation, improper waste disposal, lack of basic sanitation, pollution, and loss of biodiversity. Image 1 below shows the school and its location on the map.

Image 1: São Pedro District / EFITI José Ferreira Sobrinho School

Source: Adapted from Google Maps, 2022.

The José Ferreira Sobrinho Full-Time Elementary School (EFITI), part of the Inova Educação program, is located in the São Pedro district of Garanhuns. The elective course was developed through theoretical, practical, and field classes, enabling the analysis of the causes, consequences, and solutions to local environmental problems. The study is characterized as observational, based on bibliographic research and field classes, articulating theory and practice.

It was observed that the improper disposal of solid waste and sewage contributes to environmental degradation, aggravated by socioeconomic factors. The activities carried out, such as direct observation, environmental analysis, and classroom discussions, broadened the understanding of the environmental and social impacts of this reality. The research sought to promote an understanding of the role of Environmental Education in the school context, raising students' awareness of the improper disposal of waste in the Canhoto River and its environmental and social impacts.

METHODOLOGY

The research began with a literature review, aiming to theoretically ground the study and support the development of the elective course proposal. This stage involved the analysis of books, articles, theses, and other relevant scientific publications. According to Andrade (2010), bibliographic research contributes to the delimitation of the topic, the construction of the theoretical framework, and the support of academic analyses.

The investigation enabled the understanding of concepts related to the environment, sustainability, preservation, socio-environmental practices, Environmental Education, and a diversified curriculum, contributing to the development of contextualized pedagogical

activities. According to the National Curriculum Guidelines for Environmental Education (CNE Resolution No. 2/2012), Environmental Education should occur in an integrated, interdisciplinary, and continuous manner at all levels of education.

This research is characterized as qualitative, from the perspective of Denzin and Lincoln (2006), because it understands phenomena within their natural contexts and considers the meanings attributed by the subjects. The activities involved theoretical, practical, and field classes, including the construction of models and educational games with recyclable materials. In this context, field classes favor concrete and contextualized learning, strengthening the articulation between theory and practice, as highlighted by Roslin (2013). Thus, the elective course constituted a space for interdisciplinarity, experimentation, and critical development of the students.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Environmental education is a relevant topic in contemporary society, as it promotes awareness of environmental issues and an understanding of the relationship between people and the environment, encouraging actions aimed at preserving natural resources. Image 2 shows the location of the Canhoto River on the map.

Image 2: Location of the Canhoto River.

Source: Wikipedia, 2024.

The image above shows the location of the Canhoto River. According to Wikipedia (2024), the Canhoto River is a watercourse, that is, a river that runs through the states of Pernambuco and Alagoas, playing an important environmental and social role for local communities. Image 3 shows the course of the Canhoto River in the São Pedro District.

Image 3 : Area of the Canhoto River along its course in the São Pedro District.

Source: YouTube, adapted in 2024.

The Canhoto River, as it runs through the São Pedro District, exhibits high levels of pollution due to the improper disposal of solid waste and the discharge of domestic sewage. This problem causes environmental impacts such as water, soil, and air contamination, as well as siltation of the river caused by the accumulation of sediment in its bed.

In this context, the relationship between urban afforestation and environmental education becomes essential for the preservation of natural resources. According to Silva et al. (2023), educational practices aimed at raising public awareness contribute to environmental conservation. Afforestation helps protect waterways, reduce siltation, improve air quality, regulate temperature, and preserve biodiversity. However, the absence of educational actions favors the removal of vegetation and the improper disposal of waste in these spaces.

Given this reality, the need to rethink consumption and disposal practices becomes evident. According to Reigota (2009), Environmental Education should assume a formative and transformative character, promoting community participation and linking local problems to global environmental issues. As per the National Curriculum Parameters (1997), Environmental Education should be approached in a cross-cutting and interdisciplinary manner, integrating different areas of knowledge. This approach broadens the understanding of socio-environmental issues and fosters the development of critical awareness. Image 4 shows records of the water from the Canhoto River.

Image 4: Field trips

Source: collage, author of the research, 2023

During field trips, the environmental problems of the Canhoto River were identified through on-site visits and student reports. High levels of pollution were observed, evidenced by the water's color, intense odor, and accumulation of debris on the banks and in the riverbed. Siltation was also noted, aggravated by the absence of riparian vegetation, a factor that increases the risk of flooding during rainy periods, as occurred in 2022 due to the volume of water from the Cajarana dam.

In this context, the fragility of Environmental Education actions, both in schools and in public policies, contributes to the persistence of this reality. According to Rosa (2002), the absence of environmental education from the early years favors the distancing of individuals from nature and encourages inadequate preservation practices. Thus, the need to strengthen Environmental Education as a continuous and formative practice, promoting awareness, collective responsibility, and sustainability, becomes evident. Image 5 shows the flood in the São Pedro District.

Image 5: Floods in the São Pedro District, 2022.

Source: YouTube, adapted: 2024.

In July 2022, the São Pedro District was hit by heavy rains that caused the Canhoto River to overflow and flood homes near its banks. The event caused damage to infrastructure, material losses, and economic damage. Among the factors that contribute to this type of disaster are intense rainfall, deforestation, pollution, obstruction of the riverbed, and disordered urbanization, highlighting the need for urban planning and sustainable public policies.

As part of the elective course, two educational models were produced using recyclable materials, aiming to promote environmental awareness through practical activities. In this context, recycling and reuse are important strategies for reducing environmental impacts. According to Alves (2000), recycling contributes to the reduction of waste, the preservation of natural resources, and the development of a socio-environmental awareness focused on sustainability. Image 6 shows the construction of the models.

Image 6: Practical lesson on model making.

Source: Author of the research, 2023

The projects developed demonstrated student engagement and comprehension of the content covered. In the school context, it is possible to promote reflection on conscious consumption and proper waste disposal. According to the National Curriculum Parameters (BRASIL, 1998), the school plays a fundamental role in shaping conscious attitudes related to waste and environmental impacts.

However, the absence of a consolidated environmental culture contributes to inadequate waste disposal practices, generating impacts on the environment. This reality, observed in the São Pedro District, highlights the need to strengthen Environmental Education from basic education onwards, associated with the implementation of sustainable public policies. The articulation between theory and practice favored meaningful learning, stimulating critical thinking and the construction of socio-environmental values. In this sense, Grubel and Bez (2006) emphasize that playful activities make teaching and learning more dynamic and contribute to the construction of knowledge.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

This study made it possible to identify the environmental problems related to the pollution of the Canhoto River. The analysis highlighted the inadequate disposal of solid waste and domestic sewage as the main factors of degradation, reflecting the lack of environmental awareness and adequate infrastructure.

The investigation revealed that river pollution is associated with socioeconomic factors and insufficient public policies focused on sustainability. Furthermore, the silting process

resulting from the removal of riparian vegetation was observed, contributing to an increased risk of flooding and intensifying environmental impacts in the area.

Therefore, it is concluded that the observed environmental problems require integrated actions between environmental education, public policies, and community participation, aiming at promoting sustainable practices and preserving natural resources. It is hoped that this study will contribute to strengthening the critical awareness of the local population and to the development of future research focused on the recovery and conservation of the Canhoto River.

REFERENCES

ALVES, Ana Terezinha Jaques et al. Recycling: educating to raise awareness. **Proceedings of the II Interinstitutional Seminar on Teaching, Research and Extension. UNICRUZ**, 2012.

ANDRADE, Maria Margarida de de. Introduction to the methodology of scientific work. In: **Introduction to the methodology of scientific work** . 2010. p. 158-158.

Brazil (1977).

DA SILVA, Ismael Costa et al. Environmental perception of primary school teachers regarding urban afforestation in the school environment between 1998 and 2022. **Brazilian Journal of Environmental Education (RevBEA)** , v. 18, n. 1, p. 133-154, 2023.

DE MORAES ALVES, Jolinda; SEMZEZEM, Priscila. Social vulnerability, territorial approach and protection in social assistance policy. *Serviço Social em Revista*, v. 16, n. 1, p. 143-166, 2013.

DENZIN, NK and LINCOLN, YS Introduction: the discipline and practice of qualitative research. In: DENZIN, NK and LINCOLN, YS (Eds.). *The planning of qualitative research: theories and approaches*. 2nd ed. Porto Alegre: Artmed, 2006. p. 15-41.

DIAS, Genebaldo Freire; SALGADO, Sebastião. **Environmental education, principles and practices** . Gaia Publishing House, 2023.

FROM BRAZIL, Federal Senate. Constitution of the Federative Republic of Brazil. **Brasília: Federal Senate, Graphic Center** , 1988.

IBGE - Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics.
<https://cidades.ibge.gov.br/brasil/pe/garanhuns/panorama> .

GOMES, Yasmin Leon; PEDROSO, Daniele Saheb. Teaching methodologies in Environmental Education in Elementary School: a systematic review. **Brazilian Journal of Research in Science Education** , p. e35007-33, 2022.

GRÜBEL, JM; BEZ, MR Educational Games. 2006 Available at:

<<http://penta3.ufrgs.br/ciclo8/artigo25153.pdf>>. Accessed on: February 12, 2024.

Aerial drone footage of the village of São Pedro, district of Garanhuns, Pernambuco -
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8Nt28loap50>

MATO GROSSO DO SUL. State Department of Education. Mato Grosso do Sul Reference Curriculum: High School and New High School. Campo Grande: SED, 2021. (Reference Curriculum Series; 2). Available at:
<https://www.sed.ms.gov.br/wpcontent/uploads/2022/01/Curriculo-Novo-Ensino-Medio-v1.1.pdf>. Garanhuns – Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia. Available at:
<https://pt.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Garanhuns> .

PÁDUA, Suzana Machado. **Environmental education: paths taken in Brazil** . Ipê, 1997.

National Curriculum Parameters: Environment and Health. MEC/Brasília.

Rain causes flooding in the village of São Pedro in Garanhuns -
https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ehoFK6sd_J0 .

REIGOTA, Marcos. What is Environmental Education. São Paulo: Brasiliense, 2012.
Coleção Primeiros Passos , v. 292, 1999.

Rio Canhoto - Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia. https://pt.wikipedia.org/wiki/Rio_Canhoto .

Resolution of the National Education Council (CNE) No. 2, of June 15, 2012. Establishes the National Curriculum Guidelines for Environmental Education. Ministry of Education (MEC).

ROSA, Antônio Carlos Machado da. The main lines and methodological guidelines of environmental education. **Environmental Education: Basic Distance Learning Course: Education and Environmental Education I. Ana Lúcia Tostes de Aquino Leite and Naná Mininni-Medina (Coord). Brasília: MMA** , 2001. p. 15-32.

ROSLIN, Ma Anya Yasmin A. et al. Social impact of ecotourism on the behavior of students on educational field trips to Makiling Botanic Gardens in the University of the Philippines Los Baños. **USM R&D Journal** , vol. 17, no. 1, p. 71-80, 2009.

Garanhuns Department of Education on Instagram -
https://www.instagram.com/p/CohyhE7O3Rr/?igsh=ajR1YzN6bHZucjhw&img_index=1

WINGERT, Éverli Bier et al. Sustainable public policies: a set of alternatives for small municipalities in Rio Grande do Sul. **Electronic Journal of Administration and Tourism-ReAT** , v. 16, n. 2, p. 21-37, 2022.